

Adaptive optics: from exploring the Universe to optical control of near-Earth space

Astronomy, space surveillance and optical communications: a strategic convergence

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ABSTRACT

Adaptive optics (AO) has evolved from a specialized astronomical technique into a key enabling technology for a broad range of strategic applications, including extremely large telescopes, space situational awareness (SSA), and free-space optical (FSO) communications. These domains share a common physical challenge: the propagation of optical waves through a turbulent, dynamic, and three-dimensional atmosphere. This paper highlights the convergence between astronomy, SSA, and optical communications, emphasizing how advances in one domain have driven progress in the others. Astronomy has pushed AO systems to their ultimate performance limits, enabling high-contrast imaging and the development of tomographic techniques. SSA has introduced strong requirements in terms of robustness, real-time adaptability, and operation under highly dynamic conditions. FSO communications have extended the scope of AO to beam control and energy optimization, introducing challenges such as scintillation mitigation and uplink pre-compensation under anisoplanatic conditions.

We show that these applications now form a unified technological ecosystem, supported by common building blocks such as wavefront sensing, deformable mirrors, predictive control, and increasingly, machine learning techniques. Finally, the PROVIDENCE project is presented as a unique European facility designed to bring together these domains within a single experimental platform, enabling on-sky validation of advanced AO concepts and fostering cross-disciplinary innovation.

Keywords: Adaptive optics, space situational awareness, free-space optical communication, turbulence, predictive control, ELT, SSA, FSO

1. INTRODUCTION

As space becomes an increasingly strategic domain, the ability to control light propagation through the atmosphere has emerged as a key driver of both scientific capability and technological sovereignty. Observing, monitoring, and communicating are the three critical functions rely on a common physical reality: the transmission of an optical signal through a turbulent, dynamic, and three-dimensional medium. The performance of ground-based optical systems is no longer limited solely by telescope aperture or laser power, but by the ability to dynamically compensate for atmospheric perturbations that degrade the information carried by light.

Adaptive optics (AO), first proposed in the mid-20th century, has progressively become the technological response to this challenge. Historically associated with astronomy, AO is now a transversal cornerstone supporting extremely large telescopes, Space Situational Awareness (SSA), and Free-Space Optical (FSO) communications.

Understanding this evolution requires revisiting the physical principles that motivated its emergence and analyzing how their progressive mastery has shaped a new scientific and industrial ecosystem. It directly contributes to space sovereignty and innovation.

	Astronomy	SSA	FSO
Diameter	4 → 40 m	0.4 → 4m	0.1 → 1m
Operation	Night	Sunset / Sunrise	All day & night
FoV	Very small to large	Small	On-axis
Site selection	Best possible	As good as possible	Site diversity
Turb conditions	Good (~ 1")	Medium (2" – 4")	strong (> 4")
Flux conditions	Faint	Medium	High
KPI	SR (mostly) Sky coverage	Spatial resolution Tracking	Coupling efficiency Disponibility

Figure 1 : Key features of the various flagship OA applications.

2. ADAPTIVE OPTICS: FROM THEORETICAL CONCEPT TO CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Adaptive optics was first proposed in 1953 by Horace W. Babcock. However, the concept remained largely theoretical for several decades due to the lack of suitable technologies, in particular high-speed wavefront sensors, deformable mirrors, and real-time control systems. It was not until the 1980s that the first operational demonstrations for civilian astronomy were achieved, with major contributions from ONERA, CNRS and other leading institutions. These developments paved the way for the widespread deployment of AO systems on 8–10 meter class telescopes.

The principle of adaptive optics is conceptually straightforward: measure the distortions of the incoming wavefront using a dedicated sensor, compute the required correction in real time, and apply this correction via a deformable mirror capable of reshaping its surface at kilohertz rates.

In practice, however, this apparent simplicity conceals significant complexity. AO systems must operate in thermos-mechanically unstable environments, achieve sub-micrometer (often nanometric) precision, and handle thousands of degrees of freedom in real-time. Furthermore, they frequently operate under low-photon-flux conditions, where measurements are strongly affected by noise.

After more than four decades of continuous development, adaptive optics is now fully integrated into the core architecture of modern telescopes. This evolution marks a paradigm shift from AO as an auxiliary instrument to AO as an intrinsic component of the telescope system itself, effectively transforming telescopes into adaptive systems.

3. ASTRONOMY AS AN EXTREME LABORATORY

Astronomy provides one of the most demanding environments for adaptive optics. A particularly emblematic challenge is the direct detection of exoplanets, which requires distinguishing an object that is millions to billions of times fainter than its host star, at extremely small angular separations (from a few hundred nanoradians to a few microradians).

This challenge has been a major driver for AO development. The need for extreme contrast has led to the design of ultra-sensitive wavefront sensors, advanced calibration strategies, and predictive control algorithms. Instruments such as SPHERE installed on the Very Large Telescope represent key milestones in achieving these performance levels. L'arrivée des télescopes géants de la classe de l'Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) Européen marque une nouvelle étape. Cette infrastructure comporte 798 miroirs segmentés hexagonaux de 1,4m de diamètre et des miroirs adaptatifs dotés de milliers d'actionneurs. La reconstruction tomographique du volume turbulent, à partir de multiples étoiles laser artificielles, devient nécessaire pour corriger efficacement des champs de vue élargis et donner accès à la quasi-totalité du ciel. Associée à des instruments comme le spectro-imageur à haute résolution spatiale et spectrale HARMONI, l'ELT devrait révolutionner notre vision du cosmos dans les prochaines années.

Figure 2 the European ELT currently under construction in the Atacama Desert in Chile. The 39-meter-diameter telescope is protected by an 80-meter-high dome. It is scheduled to become operational by the end of the decade (typically around 2030).

The technological advances required to meet these extreme scientific goals have produced a robust foundation that now extends far beyond astrophysics.

4. SPACE SURVEILLANCE: ROBUSTNESS UNDER FAST DYNAMICS

Space Situational Awareness (SSA) addresses a rapidly growing strategic need: detecting, tracking, and characterizing objects in orbit, including operational satellites, space debris, and potentially hazardous objects.

Initially driven by Cold War-era requirements, this domain significantly contributed, as early as the 1970s, to the development of key adaptive optics components—wavefront sensors, deformable mirrors, and real-time control systems—leading to the first high-angular-resolution ground-based observations of space objects.

Observing satellites presents conditions that differ markedly from classical astronomy. Targets often exhibit rapid apparent motion, their attitude may change on timescales of seconds, and their brightness can vary significantly. Observations are frequently conducted at low elevation angles, where atmospheric turbulence is both stronger and more non-stationary.

In this context, adaptive optics must not only improve angular resolution but also maintain correction stability under highly dynamic conditions. Predictive control algorithms developed for astronomy find natural applications here, as do advanced image reconstruction techniques and point spread function (PSF) estimation methods in the absence of ideal reference sources.

Conversely, SSA imposes stringent operational constraints, including robustness, daytime operation capability, and the need to handle strong non-stationarities. These requirements feed back into astronomical AO developments, enhancing system reliability and adaptability.

Space situational awareness (SSA) addresses a growing strategic need: to detect, track, and characterize objects in orbit, whether they are operational satellites, debris, or potentially hazardous objects. This need, driven by the space race of the Cold War, materialized in the 1970s through a decisive effort to develop the key components of adaptive optics (wavefront sensors, deformable mirrors, real time computers) and led to the development of the first ground-based high-angular-resolution observation capabilities.

5. OPTICAL COMMUNICATIONS: CONTROLLING THE BEAM FOR TRANSMISSION

Adaptive optics also plays a critical role in optical communication systems. Whether for horizontal links over tens of kilometers or ground-to-satellite links, the primary objective is to maximize the optical power coupled into the receiving fiber, enabling high-data-rate and inherently secure transmissions due to the strong directivity of optical waves. Data

rates of several tens of gigabits per second per wavelength can be achieved. It would be equivalent to transmitting a 4K video stream in a fraction of a second

In this context, the primary concern is no longer image quality but beam quality. Atmospheric turbulence affects both the phase and intensity of the optical field, leading to scintillation and coupling losses in optical fibers. In bidirectional links, adaptive optics measures and corrects turbulence effects using the signal received from the satellite (LEO or GEO). This information is then used to pre-compensate the uplink beam transmitted from the ground. This pre-compensation introduces a fundamental challenge. Due to the propagation delay and the relative motion between the ground station and the satellite, the transmitted beam must be pointed slightly ahead of the direction of the received beam—a phenomenon known as point-ahead angle. As a result, the uplink beam propagates through a turbulent volume that differs from the one sampled by the downlink signal. This leads to a decorrelation between measured and experienced perturbations, known as anisoplanatism, which degrades the effectiveness of pre-compensation.

The FEELINGS station, developed by ONERA, aims to address these challenges and demonstrated, in 2024, a world-first high-data-rate optical transmission between ground and a geostationary satellite. Technologies developed for astronomy, in particular high-performance wavefront sensors, predictive control, and tomographic reconstruction, are directly leveraged. However, FSO introduces additional constraints, including strong scintillation effects, rapid signal fading, and the need for efficient uplink pre-compensation. This has led to the development of approaches combining phase and intensity measurements, as well as increasing integration of machine learning techniques for real-time optimization.

Finally, it is worth noting that uplink pre-compensation for optimal energy delivery through turbulence is closely related to emerging defense applications, particularly long-range directed energy systems.

6. A VIRTUOUS CYCLE OF CROSS-FERTILIZATION

Over the past four decades, one key observation stands out: major advances in adaptive optics have never remained confined to a single domain. Each breakthrough has found extension into other application fields. Today, we are witnessing the emergence of a structured technological ecosystem in which astronomy, Space Situational Awareness (SSA), and Free-Space Optical (FSO) communications interact dynamically and mutually reinforce each other.

Figure 3: The three pillars of adaptive optics: defense (space surveillance and directed-energy weapons), astronomy, and free-space optical communications. It is worth noting, as shown in the illustrations, that all of these applications use lasers (to deliver energy, transmit information, or generate artificial stars).

This convergence is first rooted in a shared physical foundation: the propagation of a coherent optical field through a turbulent, non-stationary, three-dimensional medium. Whether imaging an exoplanet, tracking a satellite, or transmitting data through the atmosphere, the fundamental question remains the same: how to measure and correct turbulence-induced distortions in real time.

6.1 A shared technological foundation

Core building blocks, wavefront sensors, deformable mirrors, real-time controllers, and predictive control algorithms, are now common across all domains. However, it is in the refinements that the depth of these synergies becomes evident. Astronomy, driven by extreme performance requirements, has led to the development of ultra-fast deformable mirrors with thousands of actuators and highly sensitive detectors operating close to the photon noise limit. The quest for full sky coverage has driven the development of laser guide stars and tomographic reconstruction techniques. Similarly, predictive control strategies, initially developed to mitigate telescope vibrations, have been extended to SSA for tracking fast-moving objects and to FSO for compensating point-ahead effects. Techniques such as Linear Quadratic Gaussian (LQG) control, variational approaches, and more recently reinforcement learning, now form a shared algorithmic framework.

Figure 4 : Synergies and differences among the three flagship applications of adaptive optics

6.2 Synergies and differences among the three flagship applications of adaptive optics

While astronomy has historically driven ultimate performance, SSA and FSO introduce complementary requirements: speed, robustness, and operation under degraded and non-stationary conditions. These constraints have led to the development of adaptive control strategies capable of updating system parameters in real time. These advances, in turn, benefit astronomical systems, especially extremely large telescopes, where internal disturbances and environmental variations also introduce significant non-stationarities.

6.3 Phase and intensity: toward a unified framework

FSO systems have highlighted the importance of intensity fluctuations (scintillation), whereas astronomy has traditionally focused on phase correction.

This has led to the development of hybrid approaches combining phase and amplitude measurements, along with spatio-angular control strategies capable of mitigating signal fading. These developments extend the classical AO framework and open new perspectives for wide-field astronomical correction.

6.4 The structuring role of artificial intelligence

The increasing number of degrees of freedom, reaching several thousands in modern systems, makes advanced machine learning techniques essential.

Reinforcement learning, data-driven predictive models, and hybrid approaches combining physical models with neural networks are transforming how AO systems are designed and operated. These tools provide a common framework applicable across all domains.

A virtuous cycle is thus emerging: astronomy pushes performance to physical limits, SSA enforces robustness and operational responsiveness, and FSO introduces energy optimization and active pre-compensation. Each domain accelerates the others' progress.

7. PROVIDENCE: A UNIQUE FACILITY IN EUROPE

Within this dynamic of cross-domain synergies, the need has emerged for an experimental platform capable of bringing together astronomy, surveillance, and optical communications within a single environment. The PROVIDENCE project addresses precisely this need. Led by ONERA in partnership with the CNRS, PROVIDENCE is developed at the Observatoire de Haute-Provence, a historic site of early end of the adaptive optics demonstrations. The project aims to deliver, by the decade, a 2.5-meter telescope optimized for high angular resolution.

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7.1 A pre-operational platform for space observation

The rapid increase in the number of objects in orbit, combined with their diversity in size, shape, and function, requires access to ground-based characterization capabilities to support sovereign space situational awareness. With the largest aperture telescope in Europe dedicated to this purpose, capable of tracking low Earth orbit (LEO) satellites, and equipped with a state-of-the-art adaptive optics system, PROVIDENCE is expected to achieve a spatial resolution on the order of 20 cm for metric-class objects at distances of ~1000 km.

with their high-resolution

Coupled with a comprehensive end-to-end modeling platform of the instrumental chain, this facility will enable systematic cataloging of orbital objects with unprecedented accuracy from the ground in Europe.

Figure 5 Artist's rendering of the Providence project, currently under construction at the OHP (scheduled to come online in late 2028)

7.2 A system architecture designed for versatility

Unlike infrastructures dedicated solely to astronomy, PROVIDENCE is conceived as a flexible system capable of supporting multiple operational modes: high-resolution astronomical observations, tracking of space objects in LEO and GEO, and experimentation with bidirectional optical communication links.

This versatility requires a modular architecture, where wavefront sensors, deformable mirrors, and control laws can be reconfigured depending on the scenario. The ability to switch between configurations optimized for faint, non-cooperative targets and those adapted to cooperative laser beacons represents a significant technical challenge and a key strength of the project.

7.3 A tool for sovereignty and training

Beyond its technological dimension, PROVIDENCE addresses a major issue of scientific and industrial sovereignty. Mastery of adaptive optics applied to space surveillance and optical communications represents a strategic advantage in a rapidly evolving geopolitical context.

By providing a national platform that federates academic, industrial, and institutional expertise, PROVIDENCE strengthens the position of France and Europe in these domains. It will also serve as a training platform for the next generation of scientists and engineers who will design and operate future complex optical systems.

8. CONCLUSION – MASTERING LIGHT AS A STRATEGIC CAPABILITY

Adaptive optics has evolved, in just a few decades, from an instrumental innovation into a cornerstone technology for the optical control of near-Earth space. It now forms a critical link between three major domains: the exploration of the Universe, the monitoring of the space environment, and the development of next-generation optical communication systems.

At the core of these applications lies a shared challenge: the real-time control of an optical field distorted by a turbulent medium. The ability to address this challenge constitutes a major scientific, technological, and strategic advantage.

As space becomes an increasingly contested and operational domain, the convergence between astronomy, Space Situational Awareness, and Free-Space Optical communications is no longer merely a scientific opportunity, it is a key driver of sovereignty and innovation for the decades to come.

Adaptive optics is thus entering a new phase of its evolution. After the eras of theoretical development, experimental demonstration, and domain-specific specialization, we are now witnessing the emergence of a paradigm of systemic integration and strategic convergence. Projects such as PROVIDENCE embody this transition in a tangible way.